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PROJECT REPORT

ON

“CUSTOMER’S CHANGING BEHAVIOR ON BANKING OPERATIONS”

BY

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ABSTRACT

The present era is of intense competition in Indian retail banking. Almost all banks are providing competitive products and services to their customers. It includes SMS, ATMs, Online Banking, Mobile Banking and many more services. Parsuraman et al. (1985) developed the service quality model at an initial stage and documented that service quality is a function of expectations of the customers and actual performance of service product through various service quality dimensions. The time when the size of overall Indian banking system has become gigantic which includes both small and large banks with huge number of branch network, one of the biggest challenge faced by banks in present time is the switching intention of the customers. Hence it becomes more important to understand that why customers in India switch from one bank to another bank. Considering this aspect, the study under consideration has focused on the switching behavior of customers in retail banking service in India. Clemes et al. (2007) has suggested nine factors influencing banking switching behavior of customers. The impact of these influence factors have been studied and tested empirically using exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Quantitative data have been collected by means of questionnaire employed from Clemes et al. and administered to 496 banking customers throughout India by using convenience sampling. Results of the study disclosed that price, customer commitment, responses to service failure, customer satisfaction, reputation, service quality, competition, service products and involuntary switching have their noteworthy effect on customers' switching behaviour. The results of present study can be used by the Indian banks for designing their product and service strategies, marketing strategies and customer services practices in order to decrease customer switching. This would also help them in improving their service operations and in increasing customer fulfilment and truthfulness by understanding the banking behaviour of their customers.

The price war and intense competition in Indian banking industry have exposed banks to one of the major threats of switching. Consumers are now more price and service conscious in their financial services purchasing behavior. They are more prone to change their banking behaviour as banking products and services are nearly identical in nature. The purpose of this paper is to provide an insight of the drivers that lead a customer switch from one service provider to another in Indian banking industry using exploratory design. Design/methodology/approach – The impacts of the influencing factors have been studied and tested empirically using exploratory factor analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Banking history can be traced from the merchant's bank of the ancient world which was initially focusing on issuing grain loans to farmers and traders around 2000BC. Later on during the Roman Empire, lenders were based in Temples and added two major innovations; they started accepting deposits (Opened and maintained customer's accounts) and changed money. The first bank was the Italian bank which was called The Medici bank (MB) established by Giovanni Medici in 1397. Banking in the modern world has developed to accommodate many changes and innovations. Banking industry has been and continues to be changed as a result of privatization of country owned banks that had conquered banking systems in the past.

Banks desires automation to be able to survive with fast-growing technology in attraction of customers in order to achieve efficient and effective operations. Banking business is different from other businesses in various ways with single significant difference being banks are used as the custodians of the customer's money. Banks are used as society's saving mechanism by accepting deposits, money lending in the process earn a reasonable spread to meet expenses concerned in carrying out intermediary business and generate adequate return. Not only that but also banks connect customers with capital deficit with those having capital surpluses, regulate country's economy mostly by controlling the flow of money in the society and facilitate international business.

As a commercial bank in Tanzania, Dcb bank (Tanzania), whose full name is Dar es Salaam Commercial bank. Providing banking services to individuals, small and medium-sized businesses as well as large corporations. As of September 2010, Dar es Salaam commercial bank (Tanzania) maintains a vast branch network covering large cities and small towns across the whole country. Thus the

number of branches maintained by the bank exceeds 90. Unfortunately, in 2013, the number of branches decreased from 90 branches to 52 branches due to bad performance of several branches to be closed.

The bank traces its origins to 1967 when the Tanzania Government nationalized Financial Institutions, including banks. In 1991, the banking industry was deregulated. The Government of Tanzania retained a 30% shareholding and the International Finance Corporation (IFC), a member of the World Bank Group took up 15% shareholding in the bank. The new entity became known as Dar es salaam commercial bank (Tanzania) Limited. Dar es Salaam commercial bank provides full Internet banking, further enhancing the capacity of its customers to do their banking from anywhere at any time. The bank also provides other traditional banking products and services including individual and business accounts, savings and current accounts, fixed deposits, overdrafts, loans, money transfers, insurance services and bureau de change.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Various researchers have identified factors that may contribute to customer satisfaction in commercial banks. Drivers of behavior change lead to a change in customer decision. In order to identify the research problem in the proposed study, the following sections discuss the findings from previous studies on behavioral change. Many researchers and authors have provided various explanations for changing behavior (as shown in Table 2). After reviewing these definitions we may conclude that a change could be a decision or process of various actions involving terminating a relationship with the same service provider and ceasing to purchase a product or service from that service provider, replacing that other service provider. Garland (2002) studied private bank trading in New Zealand using the Juster scale measurement method and concluded that the total deviation rate is 5%. Trubik and Smith (2007) examined and developed a model for identifying customers at risk of leaving banks in the Australian banking sector through a study of responsible qualifications. But this model could not be generalized because they did the research in only one organization.

Many other studies emphasize complaining behavior as pre-change behavior as Stewart (1998) reported that 80% of respondents complained to the affected bank before the change. Similarly, Colgate and Hedge (2001) have learned to adapt as an effective process that improves over time and eliminates complaints. The study concluded that factors considered to be important in losses contribute to complaining behavior. In addition to these studies on customer behavior change, few other researchers have attempted to examine post-change behavior. (Keaveney, 1995).

Colgate and Lang (2001) examined the barriers to change, a distorted event in changing drivers. This study strongly confirmed that boredom and hopelessness were the main barriers to change, respectively, in the banking and insurance

industry. Yanamandram and White (2006) examined the barriers to change but with a different framework for business-to-business services (B-2-B) and using a different approach. Their study concluded that different service providers and switching costs were two key barriers to change that prevent customers from being dissatisfied with switching. Valenzuela (2010) examined various factors that determine barriers to change and the impact of bank type, gender and education on customer perceptions of barrier change. Similarly, Tesfom and Birch (2011) saw a link between age and barriers to change in the commercial banking industry. To understand behavior change, it is important to define behavior change drivers. The next section discusses the theoretical framework and definition of operational change drivers. Changing a bank is the result of many things and not just one as bank customers have a stronger relationship with their service providers (Gerrard and Cunningham, 2004). Keaveney (1995) provided the first model of behavior change in the service industry based on the more than 800 critical events that led customers to change their banks. He further categorized the incidents into eight variable causes such as number, disruption, contextual service failure, competition problems, staff response failure due to service failure, failure to meet needs, ethical issues and default features. The study was based on 45 categories of services including the services of commercial banks. But the model provided by this study requires further testing of customer behavior in the retail banking industry. (Keaveney, 1995; Mittal and Lassar, 1998) In the following table features used to study banking transformation in India, it is discussed.

To understand behavior change, it is important to define behavior change drivers. The next section discusses the theoretical framework and definition of operational change drivers. Changing a bank is the result of many things and not just one as bank customers have a stronger relationship with their service providers (Gerrard and Cunningham, 2004). Keaveney (1995) provided the first model of

behavior change in the service industry based on the more than 800 critical events that led customers to change their banks. He also categorized the incidents into eight variable causes such as number, disruption, contextual service failure, competition problems, staff response failure due to service failure, failure to meet requirements, ethical issues and default features. The study was based on 45 categories of services including the services of retail banks. But the model provided by this study requires further testing of customer behavior in the retail banking industry. (Keaveney, 1995; Mittal and Lassar, 1998) In the following table features used to study banking transformation in India, it is discussed.

Banks have come up with the idea of mobile banking that attracts more people in developed and developing countries. The ratio between the mobile user and the mobile banking user is very small. Mobile user numbers are higher than those of bank users. It provides an opportunity for banks to take advantage of a mobile user and get them to agree on the use of a mobile bank. Provides banking facilities from home and office. Internet banking requires a personal computer and an internet connection, which serve as a limitation. Mobile banking solves the problem of online banking and comes up with a slogan to satisfy consumer demand. Provides service anytime, anywhere online. Lack of awareness among the people, associated costs and lack of access have led to a decline in the number of mobile banking users.

Provides transparency in user performance and even flow followed by user and government. The researcher placed emphasis on achieving a level of consumer awareness and identified ways in which additional awareness is created. The books will highlight consumer awareness opportunities and attitudes about mobile banks. A study by Al-Ashban and Burney [4] found that fluctuations in demographics have an impact on attitudes and a few other factors such as technology-saving technologies and behavior in banking technology. A. Mobile

Banking Evolution in India The adoption of mobile technology by the banking sector has served as a boon to the industry's growth. Among Asian countries, India is actively embracing mobile communication. The adoption of mobile communications has given the banking industry the opportunity to perform various financial functions. The use of technology-focused financial services is not a new concept in the banking sector. In the year, 1987 HSBC established and installed its first ATM. Ongoing changes have been made to expand and empower the banking sector. It has provided many financial services to the consumer over the past two decades. Every year, new 1991 mobile banking ideas (mobile banking) come to India. ICICI became the first bank to provide portable banking and later HDFC and IDBI banks came up with the same idea. Technology has made it possible for people to use resources that have transformed the financial industry. Some names for mobile banking can be called providing services between consumers and the bank. Mobile banking provides the consumer with easy access to banking services using a handheld device. They can use various functions such as debt repayment, loans, installments, purchases etc. It is the next generation bank where financial resources will be in everyone's hands. Mobile banking provided customer satisfaction as the user can use 24x7 services which reduces administrative costs and hosting costs. The user feels that mobile banking provides better services compared to banks. Banks include M-commerce which became famous in 2007. Mobile banking depends on your network service provider. Maintaining internet speed can make the job more successful.

The Government of India and the Reserve Bank of India have promoted the provision of mobile banking services to customers. Therefore, through available literature proves that automation plays an important role in shaping human life. A cell phone is a way of life for everyone. Cell phones are like a shadow to us and portable banking is an effective way to provide banking services. India still has a strong market to expand mobile banking services. B. Consumer Awareness

Marketing means consumer awareness. Consumer awareness is defined as understanding the product or services and their environment by the consumer. Mobile banking awareness can be enhanced by commercial advertising, word of mouth and collaboration. The user should feel the value and importance of the mobile bank in his daily activities. The bank strives to provide mobile banking users with customized services to attract and encourage them to use the mobile banking service on a regular basis. The number of users is only increased by raising awareness among themselves and directing them to use mobile banking. A study by Dasgupta, Paul, and Fuloria [5] confirms the future of mobile banking in India. C. Consumer Attitude towards the New Technological Innovation called the technological revolution has important implications for normal human life and work. The expansion of IT (information technology) has entered the lives of millions of people. Significant changes in the global economic and business climate have been seen as a result of rapid technological advances. The attitude developed after using a portable banking system is based on previous experience and expertise [6]. Patel [7] said the user is ready to use mobile banking but is afraid of password integrity, privacy, data encryption, and hacking. Mobile banking requires consumer involvement [8]. Steps are taken to build a customer relationship. Technology has impacted all sectors.

According to Bradley and Steward [9] many industries are starting to go banking online. The financial service provider accepts the change as soon as it becomes easier and more convenient for them to contact the customer. The Sinha and Sinha study [10] said that the banking sector created awareness and awareness in the consumer's mind about the services provided by the bank. In addition, it reflects innovation and innovation in banking services. It is an exchange of the traditional way of making a transaction.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Objective

The objective of the study is to study whether the net profit and closing stock of a bank act as a factor in improving the customer satisfaction by doing a spearman ranked correlation on Indian Customer Satisfaction Index.

Objective of the Study

The research is conducted to address the following objectives:

- ✓ To study the relation between customer satisfaction and service quality of bank.
- ✓ To study the relation between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.
- ✓ To study the relation between customer loyalty & service quality of bank.

Data

The entire study is based on the analysis done on data publicly available from the ICSI. The ICSI [Indian Customer Satisfaction Index] is introduced and maintained by Hexagon consulting a Delhi based management consulting firm that is in collaboration with the globally respected US based organisation American Customer Satisfaction Index(ACSI). The financial data for the banks taken under study were obtained from Capitaline database. Capitaline database is a sister concern of capital market, which specialized in data collection and standardization of financial institutions.

After doing a thorough analysis of the existing literature we found that the questionnaire developed by the Clemes et al. (2007) is appropriate for current study. The questionnaire is having two sub parts: first describing the demographic profile of the respondents and second part is having thirty one statements regarding the features of service and other statement that might affect the customer's switching behavior.

Data has been collected from retail banking customers having at least one saving bank account in any public or private sector bank in India. For the collection of data a questionnaire having 7 point likert scale (1 strongly agree and 7 is strongly

disagree) for different statements was sent to 340 banking customers by using convenient sampling method. To have advantage of immediate retrieval, exit intercept survey method was used to have information from the respondents (Zhou, 2004). Questionnaires were filled personally to maximize the response rate and it intended that the researchers were on hand to answer queries. Total of 247 questionnaires were collected back and out of these questionnaire 235 completed questionnaires were used for the further analysis in the current study. Few questionnaires were removed because of high response bias and some data were also missing. Similarly, HNI (high net worth individuals) customers were not the part of final data for analysis as they do not visit the bank branches in person so we cannot rely on their responses. On the similar ground base layer customers were also removed from the current study.

For the analysis of the data statistical package SPSS 23 was used and data reduction technique of factor analysis was used to assess the dimensionality of the reasons why customers switch banks. Descriptive statistics were also utilized to check the relative importance of the factors determining switching behavior of customers.

Out of 235 respondents 69 were switcher and remaining 166 are non-switcher. Above analysis of the demographic profile shows that older bank customers are unwilling to switch their main bank in comparison to the younger customers and this is in consistent with the findings of the Clames et al. (2010). Approximately 60% of the respondents have accounts in public sector banks and 39% have bank account in private sector bank. 80% approx. of the respondents are involved in multi-banking and remaining 20% is having single service provider relationship.

Table represents different driver of switching behaviour of banking customers, from highest to lowest on the basis of their mean value on a scale of 1-7. The mean value scores of all the mentioned factors/statements/ drivers of switching ranges from 3.80 to 4.65 but this does not notify that all factors are of greater importance as not a single value is close to the highest value of seven point scale. Service quality and customer commitment statements/drivers are the important factors among all the constructs considered in the study.

Results of demographic profile of the respondents are shown in the following table in detail.

Description of demographic

	<i>Total Respondents</i>		<i>Switcher</i>		<i>Non-switchers</i>	
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Age of the respondent</i>						
24-years or less	62	26.38	19	27.15	63	37.8
25-34	47	20.00	15	21.33	37	22.12
35-44	53	22.55	15	21.98	32	19.47
45-54	32	13.62	11	15.29	19	11.29
55-years and above	38	16.17	10	14.25	14	8.17
Missing	3	1.28	0	0	2	1.15
Total	235		69	100	166	100
<i>Gender</i>						
Male	179	76.17	54	78.26	132	79.52
Female	53	22.55	11	15.94	34	20.48
Missing	3	1.28	4	5.80	0	0.00
Total	235		69	100.00	166	100.00
<i>Qualification</i>						
upto 10 th	49	20.85	7	10.14	21	12.65
10+2	57	24.26	9	13.04	44	26.51
Graduation	72	30.64	19	27.54	53	31.93
post-graduation and above	53	22.55	32	46.38	46	27.71
Missing	4	1.70	2	2.90	2	1.20
Total	235		69	100.00	166	100.00
<i>Occupation</i>						
College Student	16	6.81	3	4.35	11	6.63
Housewife	8	3.40	0	0	3	1.81

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Introduction

To a large extent banks in Tanzania has brought about positive changes in the standard of living of people who access the services. Although some of the customers have not benefited, a number of the bank's customers have benefited positively. Therefore, the main objective of this study was to assess the customers' switching behavior on banking performance in Tanzania. Thus, this chapter presents the summary, conclusion and recommendations on the basis of the study findings.

Summary

The main objective of the study was to assess the customers' switching behavior on banking performance. There were factors that contributed to customers' switching banks and their influence on banking performance. DCB was chosen as a Case study, the purposive sampling and simple random sampling were used to obtain a representative size of the sample. A sample size consisted of 30 respondents; whereby 20 respondents out of 30 were interviewed as existing customers, non existing customers and bank officers. This was done through interviews, questionnaires and observations. The qualitative analysis through explanatory technique was used basing on the percentages of data collected from the field.

Conclusions

It can be concluded from the research questions and findings of this study that; customers' switching behavior in banking industry has a great impact on banking performance due to high price charged on the products, inconvenience of the bank services, effective advertising of competing banks, and lack of good service that influence customers to switch especially high income earners within the banks.

Factors that influence customers' switching in banking industry

Price

Price in banking industry refers to fee implementation, bank charges, interest on loans, interest for saving account and deposits. Price is consideration of what one pays for the benefit or service customers get from another. Later researcher (Kiser 2002) also found that price was the most influential factor that determined the customers in their switching behavior. The study revealed that the price element

in a banking industry induce the customers to switch over from one bank to another bank. The findings reveal that the service charges by the bank are very high that almost 50% of customers do not afford to pay. In order to retain customers, banks should not only rely on increasing prices for their benefits because doing so could bring downside effects to banks since price has the first impression to the customer once he/she wants to purchase a product.

The location of the bank and customer's homes/ business premises

Location is a crucial factor that could determine the bank switching behavior. People may prefer to select the nearest branch of a bank from their either residential place or work place (Kisser, 2002). Convenient location is the one of the important factors that influences the bank selection decision. The study reveals that customer switching ratio was much attributed to the long distance covered by the banks customers to and from their premises since customers use their time and spending a lot of money in order to get bank services while there is other banks nearby their premises.

Effective Advertising of competing banks

Advertising is concerned with promoting the products or services of a brand or organization for the purpose of letting the consumers know the existence of it (Clemes, et al., 2007; Cengizet et al., 2007). Advertising

efficiency has a direct positive effect on bank image as well as customer expectation. Promoting the business through announcing various offers attracted more customers. Attractions such as free gifts or lucky draw may help reduce the switching behaviour (Gerrard& Cunningham, 2004). Advertising is very important to all the banks in this highly competitive market and it seems to be the most popular way of marketing. Thus, the study reveals that effective advertisement of competing banks is one of the important determinants which influence the customers to switch banks. Since efficient advertising has a direct positive effect on bank image as well as customer expectation, and therefore, the management has to keep in touch on advertising the products by letting customers know what is going on and keeping them coming in the bank.

Factors that influence customers' switching in relation to bank services

Customer satisfaction is highly correlated with the quality of service offered by the bank. Earlier studies found that service quality had positive relationship with customer behaviours (Clemes, et al., 2007). However, the study reveals that unsatisfactory quality of service offered encourages customers to switch banks. Quality of services are denoted by politeness of the bank officials when dealing with customers, the ability of the staff to convey trust and solving customer's problems is highly demanded simply because it influences the decision of the customers whether to switch or not to switch bank

Responses on income distribution

High switching rate has been influential on high income earners since the study revealed negative effects in various angles of the bank being in organizations customers' stability in which the cost for replacement is not guaranteed. The instability of customers has a great impact on banking performance and therefore it has contributed to low profit as a result of poor performance in banking industry.

Recommendations

Due to the findings obtained from the study, the following recommendations have been made basing on the objectives of the study:

Factors that influence customers' switching in banking industry

High price was identified as the important factor that influences the customers to switch banks; and if customers feel that charges are too high, they may leave the bank and decide to find the bank which can provide affordable charges. Thus, banks should not only base on increasing prices for their benefits because doing so could bring downside effects to banks since price has the first impression to the customer once he/she wants to

purchase a product. To improve the service quality, it is suggested that the bank's staff be trained on ethics, professionalism, duties and responsibilities towards customers. However, since customers use their time and spending a lot of money in order to get bank services while other banks are nearby their premises, the management has to ensure that banks services are conveniently available

everywhere to ensure that customers are retained rather than switching to their banks. Furthermore, effective advertising should be enhanced within the bank so as to make customers aware of the new products of the bank.

Factors that influence customers' switching in relation to bank services

Banks should not ignore to provide services at a standard way to ensure that customers are satisfied. Therefore, standard of service has to be enhanced once confidence, efficiency, effectiveness of the service, and the ability of staff to get the customer's problems solved are maintained. To improve the service quality; it is important that the bank staff are well trained on ethics, professionalism, duties and responsibilities towards customers. It is expected that the staff would be articulate when explaining a product to customers to avoid confusion. A better service quality will undoubtedly attract new customers and retain the existing customers, since businesses these days are customer-centric. Thus, managers have to direct efforts and resources in the most effective and efficient way to prevent customers' departure and reduce business losses in the long run that result from customers' switching banks.

Banks who try to attract new customers from their competitors will also benefit from an understanding of what factors cause customers to switch banks. Thus, bank managers can make use of such information to develop appropriate strategies to attract new customers. Therefore, in general the greater the knowledge the bank management has about the factors affecting their customers' switching behavior, the greater the ability to develop appropriate strategies to reduce bank switching

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